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PERCEPTIONS OF PERSPECTIVE TEACHERS' TOWARDS MODERNIZATION
IN RELATION TO THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

Open Learning

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Abstract

The study is aimed at finding out the perceptions of perspective teachers of different socio-economic –status towards the modernization. Sample comprised of 422 perspective teachers from randomly selected five colleges of education affiliated to the Panjab University, Chandigarh. The main findings of the study indicated that the perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly on their attitude towards modernization. Perspective teachers from urban background and of high and low SES differ significantly on their attitude towards modernization whereas perspective teachers from rural background and of high and low SES have no difference in their attitude towards modernization. The male and female perspective teachers have no significant difference in their attitude towards modernization. Male perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly whereas female perspective teachers of high and low SES have no significant difference in their attitude towards modernization.

1.0 Introduction

Modern age is an age of science and technology. In every way we are at the verge of

entering into a new era of life in the 21st century. Almost everything stands changed under the impact of science and technology. This changing process brings changes in the social structure. No society in this world can escape from the process of change and transformation. Different types of machines, vehicles of transport are the result of change and progress. Not only this phenomenon but many new varied and complicated problems are confronting human life in all the fields. Human mind is endeavoring to find their solution through research and investigations.

As the external world is changing, changes also came into the human mind. Every human has different perception for these changes. They have different point of view; differ in their interest; habits; intelligence; aptitude; and attitude etc.

Societies are changing rapidly. To cope up with the changes in society the process of education has also to change. The education today is deliberately linked with development. Education has a purpose and this purpose is largely self-determination. It is well recognized that education influences and is inflected by the rapid scientific and technological advances which are taking place all over the world.

Modernization is a term in sociology is used to denote complex process of social change from traditional way of living and thinking. Modernization is historically inescapable and even irretrievable process of social change which has been in a very wide sense, going on ever since man has come out of his ice age and discovered the fire. However, in narrow and specific sense, the term can denote the changes that have occurred and are occurring now in the various societies of the world since the advent of European renaissance and the age of reason with the emphasis on rationality and scientific thinking. This marked a definite break with the fresh rendering of social political structure of society and the universe.

New ways of thinking or doing which are possible through education may be called modernization. Modernization is the process of transforming the old traditional societies and nations to the modernity in the field of economics, technology, industrial and social advancement. Modernization is not westernization purely. The modernized society believes in co-existence, co-operation and compromise rather in competition and conflict.

The word modernization refers to a process and not a position or a static phenomenon. It

involves the concept at becoming modern, not just being so. It is comprehensive as well as complex. It has different aspects and features. It may stand for contemporary in time and also contemporary in spirit. Modernity is a question of outlook and not of date. Modernity is generally regarded as a process of change. Change of traditional society into a society based on science and technology. A modern society is characterized among another things basically by its adoption of science based technology and growth of big complex (Apter, 1966).

Modernization involves not only the change in the material culture of a nation but also its belief system, values and a way of life on the whole. In fact modernization is the process which brings desired change in the social structure, value orientation, motivations and norms. It is process of transformation of society from its backward framework to a forward-looking progressive build up (Connell,1965).

Modernization has many dimensions. It may be perceived at social level, group level or individual level. It may also be perceived as economic modernization, political modernization, social modernization, educational modernization, technological modernization and so forth. Thus, the term 'modern' is applied not only to man, but to nations, to economics, to cities, and to institutions, etc. Modernization is erratically a process of social change a movement from traditional or quasi-traditional order to certain desired type of technology and social structure, value orientations, motivations and norms. Sociologically, modernization implies the transformation from a traditional, rural, agrarian society to a secular, urban, industrial society.

Modernization:-

- Is progressive change in all areas of life.
- signifies progress,
- Is the outcome of the development and application of scientific and technological knowledge.
- Implies feeling for others.
- Is rational thinking and rational actions.

Modernization is not:-

- Westernization.

- Just superficial acquisition of certain values.
- Anti-moral or anti-religious.

A great deal of confusion, ambiguity and variation exists regarding the meaning and concept of *socio-economic status* among different researches in the field of sociology and education. Some associate it with occupation of the family whereas other names it to the total environment, which include occupation and education of parents or in the family structure variable such as family size.

The dictionary meaning of socio-economic status is an indicator of an individual's or family's social ranking based on such factors as level of education, income and type of education.

In the modern society, an individual is judged by his social status. The social status of an individual is his position within the social relationships. It is that specific position of the individual in his relationships with other individuals by virtue of which the individual exerts influence which is being known by the symbols or signs and actions of the respect tendered to him. The status is achieved on the basis of occupation, membership of certain clubs, associations and organizations, type of house in which a person lives. Economic factors play also very important role in determining social status, which includes the total income of the family, savings and capacity to collect money in emergency. Thus, socio-economic status means any group of persons coming closer to each other on the continuum of occupation, education, income, caste and culture.

The Indian society displays marked differences in socio-economic divisions of people; individual nutrition level, medical facilities educational opportunities and other aspects of life are controlled by the existing socio-economic level of a family. In general, socio-economic status is the social and economic position of the individual in the society. The Individual who has high standing in the community and good income and lives in a well furnished home of good quality is said to have good socio-economic status.

We are living in an age at change. Every individual is now facing a world of increased modernization in which his adjective capacities are strained. Indian society and its schools and college are broadly affected by the process at modernization. There is lot of change in the way of

thinking due to modernization. It has influenced not only our way of thinking but also our way of living. A modern society traditionally rigid but attuned to adjustment between the rich heritage and the accelerated change in the modern world. The present research is a humble attempt to investigate perceptions of perspective teachers towards modernization in relation to their socio-economic status.

2.0 Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the attitude of perspective teachers towards modernization.
2. To compare the attitude of male and female perspective teachers towards modernization.
3. To compare the attitude of perspective teachers of different socio-economic status towards modernization.
4. To compare the attitude of rural and urban perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.
5. To compare the attitude of male perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.
6. To compare the attitude of female perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.

3.0 Hypotheses of the Study:

1. Perspective teachers have a neutral attitude towards modernization.
2. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male and female perspective teachers towards modernization.
3. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.
4. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.
5. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of female perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.
6. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of urban perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.

7. There exists no significant difference in the attitude of rural perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization.

4.0 Methodology

4.1 Sample

The sample of the present investigation consists of 422 students of Colleges of Education affiliated to the Panjab University, Chandigarh. The sample was drawn randomly from the five colleges of education and details of sample distribution are given in the Table 1

Table 1: Distribution of the Sample

Gender		Locality	
Male	Female	Rural	Urban
187	235	198	224

4.2 Tools used

To assess the attitude of perspective teachers towards modernization and their Socio-Economic Status following tools were used:

- Comprehensive modernization inventory: Developed and standardized by Dr. S. P. Ahluwalia (1998).
- Socio- Economic Status Scale : Developed and standardized by S.D. Kapoor And R. N. Singh (1998).

5.0 Results Interpretation

In order to analyze and interpret the data, the statistical techniques like Frequency Distribution, Mean, Standard Deviation & t-Ratio were used. The analysis of data has been presented in the following tables:

5.1 Over All Attitude

The frequency distribution of the Attitude of Perspective Teachers towards Modernization is given in the Table 2.

Table.2: Frequency Distribution of Attitude of Perspective Teachers towards Modernization

Scores	Frequency	%age of Children
160 and above	4	0.94
150-159	28	6.63
140-149	52	12.32
130-139	78	18.48
120-129	87	20.61
110-119	76	18.01
100-109	68	16.11
90-99	29	6.87

From the table 2, it is evident that all the 422 perspective teachers responded with score above than 91 indicating that all the perspective teachers have a favorable attitude towards modernization. The data thus provide a strong indication that those perspective teachers have a positive attitude towards modernization and various modern social changes.

5.2 Attitude of Male and Female Perspective Teachers

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for Male and Female Perspective teachers is given.

Table.3: Comparison of Attitude of High and Low SES Perspective Teachers towards Modernization

Variable	M ₁	M ₂	SD ₁	SD ₂	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	25.83	26.04	3.48	3.21	0.650	Not Significant

P-C Relationship	25.60	25.84	3.41	3.68	0.695	Not Significant
Politics	25.82	24.89	3.97	3.09	2.76**	Significant
Status of Women	25.47	26.30	3.83	3.31	2.41*	Significant
Marriage	25.22	26.14	4.22	3.87	2.35*	Significant
Religion	26.19	25.44	3.37	3.19	2.36*	Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	24.81	25.43	3.74	3.26	1.83	Not Significant
Total	178.94	180.08	10.06	9.81	1.18	Not Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

**Significant at .01 level of significance.

M_1 & SD_1 = Mean and Standard Deviation of High SES Group ($N_1 = 187$)

M_2 & SD_2 = Mean and Standard Deviation of Low SES Group ($N_2 = 235$)

Table 3, indicates that the calculated value of 't' is less than the tabulated value of 't', so, the statistical null hypothesis 2 stating that 'There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male and female perspective teachers towards modernization' is accepted. Hence, the analysis suggests that perspective male and female teachers have no difference in their attitude towards modernization. However, the mean scores of female perspective teachers (180.08) has been found to be higher than that of their male counterparts, who had mean score of 178.94. On the various dimensions of modernization like Education; Parent- Child Relationship; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no significant difference. But on dimensions like Politics; Status of Women; Marriage; and Religion; the male and female perspective teachers differ significantly.

5.3 Attitude of Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio

on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for High and Low SES Perspective teachers is given.

Table.4: Comparison of Attitude of High and Low SES Perspective Teachers towards Modernization

Variable	M ₁	M ₂	SD ₁	SD ₂	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	27.13	27.08	3.6	3.33	0.25	Not Significant
P-C Relationship	22.98	23.39	2.93	2.77	2.99**	Significant
Politics	27.48	26.52	4.45	3.77	4.46**	Significant
Status of Women	21.87	21.24	3.42	2.96	4.34**	Significant
Marriage	27.31	25.71	3.12	3.48	9.41**	Significant
Religion	23.24	23.06	3.31	3.04	0.03	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	27.19	27.11	3.47	3.61	1.11	Not Significant
Total	177.2	174.3	10.1	9.06	2.23*	Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

**Significant at .01 level of significance.

M₁ & SD₁ = Mean and Standard Deviation of High SES Group (N₁ = 131)

M₂ & SD₂ = Mean and Standard Deviation of Low SES Group (N₂ = 152)

Table 4 shows that the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value of 't', so, the statistical null hypothesis 3 stating that 'There exists no significant difference in the attitude of perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization' is rejected at .05 level of significance. The mean scores of high SES perspective teachers (177.2) have been found to be higher than that of their low SES counterparts, who had mean score of 174.3. It indicates that

high and low SES teacher trainees have different attitude towards modernization. On the various dimensions of modernization like Education; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no significant difference. But on dimensions like Parent- Child Relationship; Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage; the perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly.

5.4 Attitude of Male Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for Male Perspective teachers of High and Low SES is given.

Table.5: Comparison of Attitude of Male Perspective Teachers High and Low SES towards Modernization

Variable	M ₁	M ₂	SD ₁	SD ₂	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	26.84	25.14	3.67	3.82	2.43*	Significant
P-C Relationship	24.67	25.19	3.13	3.18	0.882	Not Significant
Politics	26.62	24.02	3.64	3.76	3.76**	Significant
Status of Women	26.48	24.56	3.97	4.06	2.56**	Significant
Marriage	24.17	26.43	4.09	3.93	3.01**	Significant
Religion	25.71	25.07	3.36	3.57	0.989	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	26.34	25.12	3.84	3.25	1.83	Not Significant
Total	180.83	175.53	11.04	10.61	2.62**	Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

**Significant at .01 level of significance.

M_1 & SD_1 = Mean and Standard Deviation of High SES Group ($N_1 = 59$)

M_2 & SD_2 = Mean and Standard Deviation of Low SES Group ($N_2 = 55$)

From table 5, it can be observed that the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value of 't', so, the statistical null hypothesis 4 stating that 'There exists no significant difference in the attitude of male perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization' is rejected at .01 level of significance. The mean scores of male perspective teachers of high SES (180.83) have been found to be higher than that of their male counterparts of low SES, who had mean score of 175.53. It indicates that male teacher trainees of high and low SES have different attitude towards modernization. On the various dimensions of modernization like Parent- Child Relationship; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no significant difference. But on dimensions like Education; Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage; the male perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly.

5.5 Attitude of Female Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for Female Perspective teachers of High and Low SES is given.

Table.6: Comparison of Attitude of Female Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES towards Modernization

Variable	M_1	M_2	SD_1	SD_2	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	25.45	24.14	3.61	3.47	2.33*	Significant
P-C Relationship	25.36	25.11	3.84	3.71	0.418	Not Significant
Politics	26.18	24.82	3.69	3.22	2.47*	Significant
Status of Women	26.64	25.07	4.11	3.88	2.48*	Significant
Marriage	24.12	25.93	3.43	3.81	3.16**	Significant

Religion	25.96	25.06	2.99	3.16	1.85	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	25.04	24.59	3.29	3.52	0.837	Not Significant
Total	178.75	174.72	9.96	9.34	2.63**	Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance. **Significant at .01 level of significance.

M_1 & SD_1 = Mean and Standard Deviation of High SES Group ($N_1 = 84$)

M_2 & SD_2 = Mean and Standard Deviation of Low SES Group ($N_2 = 75$)

Table 6, shows that the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value of 't', so, the statistical null hypothesis 5 stating that 'There exists no significant difference in the attitude of female perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization' is rejected at .01 level of significance. The mean scores of female perspective teachers of high SES (178.75) have been found to be higher than that of their female counterparts of low SES, who had mean score of 174.72. It indicates that female teacher trainees of high and low SES have different attitude towards modernization. On the various dimensions of modernization like Parent- Child Relationship; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no significant difference. But on dimensions like Education; Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage; the female perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly.

5.6 Attitude of Urban Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for Urban Perspective teachers of High and Low SES is given

Table.7: Comparison of Attitude of Urban Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES towards Modernization

Variable	M_1	M_2	SD_1	SD_2	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	26.73	26.22	3.38	3.52	1.45	Not Significant

P-C Relationship	21.22	21.29	2.59	3.24	0.261	Not Significant
Politics	27.1	26.21	3.26	3.52	2.55*	Significant
Status of Women	28.64	26.49	3.75	3.91	5.40**	Significant
Marriage	28.72	27.01	3.91	3.67	4.31**	Significant
Religion	23.9	23.61	2.93	3.27	0.969	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	23.55	23.48	3.07	2.82	0.251	Not Significant
Total	179.86	174.01	9.62	8.98	2.38*	Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

**Significant at .01 level of significance.

M_1 & SD_1 = Mean and Standard Deviation of Urban High SES Group ($N_1=66$)

M_2 & SD_2 = Mean and Standard Deviation of Urban Low SES Group ($N_2=78$)

Table 7, indicates that the calculated value of 't' is more than the tabulated value of 't', so, the statistical null hypothesis 6 stating that 'There exists no significant difference in the attitude of urban perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization' is rejected at .05 level of significance. The mean scores of urban perspective teachers of high SES (179.86) have been found to be higher than that of their urban counterparts of low SES, who had mean score of 174.01. It indicates that urban teacher trainees of high and low SES have different attitude towards modernization. On the various dimensions of modernization like Education; Parent- Child Relationship; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no significant difference. But on dimensions like Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage; the urban perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly.

5.7 Attitude of Rural Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES

In the following table the information on arithmetic mean, standard deviation and t-ratio on the attitude adjusted on continuous scale, for Rural Perspective teachers High and Low SES is given.

Table.8: Comparison of Attitude of Rural Perspective Teachers of High and Low SES towards Modernization

Variable	M ₁	M ₂	SD ₁	SD ₂	t-ratio	Remarks
Education	23.15	21.8	4.09	3.79	2.65*	Significant
P-C Relationship	24.55	23.12	2.51	3.26	4.37**	Significant
Politics	24.4	24.7	3.36	2.68	0.869	Not Significant
Status of Women	24.35	22.6	2.85	3.81	4.66**	Significant
Marriage	22.41	21.24	3.28	3.17	3.36**	Significant
Religion	25.36	25.6	3.61	2.69	0.646	Not Significant
Socio-Cultural Factors	22.41	22.28	2.84	2.52	0.443	Not Significant
Total	166.63	161.34	10.78	9.68	3.11**	Significant

*Significant at .05 level of significance.

**Significant at .01 level of significance.

M₁ & SD₁ = Mean and Standard Deviation of Rural High SES Group (N₁ =66)

M₂ & SD₂ = Mean and Standard Deviation of Rural Low SES Group (N₂ = 78)

It can be revealed from the table Table 7, that the calculated value of ‘t’ is more than the tabulated value of ‘t’, so, the statistical null hypothesis 7 stating that ‘There exists no significant difference in the attitude of rural perspective teachers of high and low SES towards modernization’ is rejected at .01 level of significance. The mean scores of rural perspective teachers of high SES (166.63) have been found to be higher than that of their rural counterparts of low SES, who had mean score of 161.34. It indicates that rural teacher trainees of high and low SES have different attitude towards modernization. On the various dimensions of modernization like Politics; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the two groups have no

significant difference. But on dimensions like Education ; Parent- Child Relationship; Status of Women; and Marriage; the urban perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly.

6.0 Discussion and Conclusion

The main objective of the study was to determine the attitude of perspective teachers towards modernization. The study has suggested that in the overall scenario perspective teachers have a favourable attitude towards modernization.

The present investigation has revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female perspective teachers towards modernization. In this period of social change, everyone is aware about the various new dimensions of the society and the results indicated that teacher trainees are ready to accept and adopt these social changes irrespective of gender. The male and female perspective teachers differ significantly on dimensions like Politics; Status of Women; Marriage; and Religion.

The perspective teachers of high and low SES have significant difference in their attitude towards modernization. Due to the variation in SES, the male and female perspective teachers belonging to high and low SES have a significant difference in their attitude towards modernization.

The male perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly on dimensions like Education; Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage. The female perspective teachers of high and low SES differ significantly on dimensions like Education; Politics; Status of Women; and Marriage. However, on the various dimensions of modernization like Parent- Child Relationship; Religion; and Socio-Cultural Factors; the low SES, male and female perspective teachers have no significant difference. It indicates that the low SES male and female perspective teachers are not accepting the social changes about education equality, equal status of women, marriage decisions and involvement of females in politics.

The high and low SES perspective teachers of urban area significantly differ on their attitude towards modernization. The variation in attitude towards modernization amongst rural perspective teachers of high and low SES may be attributed to the lack of acceptance to the new

social changes by the low SES group. It indicates that social change is bound to SES in the rural as well as urban areas of India.

On the various dimensions of modernization like parent- child relationship; politics; status of women; and marriage; the perspective teachers of high SES have high mean scores than their counterparts. It shows that in high SES groups there is a change in attitude regarding parent- child relationship, politics, status of women and marriage. It is the sign of great change as the Indian people have started to think about the women education, status of women and marriage decisions.

The urban perspective teachers are sensitive regarding the parent- child relationship; status of women; and marriage. The high SES group perspective teachers in urban and rural areas irrespective of gender significantly differ from the perspective teachers of low SES group. It indicates that education, economic position and status of family fasten the social change. The teachers at their training level should be motivated to accept the new norms of modernity by keeping in mind the traditional Indian values and ethics. It can be done by organizing workshops, seminars and conferences to develop a positive attitude in them towards various dimensions of social change. The people of low SES should be guided to accept and adopt the new norms of modernization as India can't be a developed nation if we are not ready to accept the modernization in a positive and constructive sense.

7.0 References:

- Apter, D.E. (1966). *The Politics of Modernization*. The University of Chicago Press: Chicago.
- Bernstein, H. (1971). "Modernization theory and the sociological study of development". *Journal of Development Studies*. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modernization>
- Biersted, R. (1957). *The Social Order*. London. Inc. p.206.
- Brugger, B. and ; Kate, H. (1983). *Modernisation and revolution*. Routledge. ISBN 0709906951.
- Connell, J. (1965). *A Concept of Modernization*. South Atlantic Quarterly, Vol.64, Autumn.